

Research

Social Media Behavior among the College Students in a Transnational Environment: A Comparative Case Study

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Abstract: The exponential growth of social media has fundamentally reshaped the world education system. Many researchers note that social media would facilitate the transition of students from high school to college by providing them with information and social support and a way to recognize and communicate with other students. Social networking is a consumer-generated tool that helps users to exchange information using the Internet with friends and colleagues. Sharing ensures that it is easy to comment on, easy to send, there are no costs associated with accessing the media, and last but not least, it is always available. In social media practices, users primarily belong to a new generation of customers who in the sense of social media, can be referred to as digital natives. Therefore, this study aimed to identify Social media behavior among College Students in a Transnational Environment. The survey method was used to collect data to satisfy this goal. The sample was selected from individuals at Wuhan University who were studying in China. The questionnaires were distributed to 250 students from international and 250 students of Chinese origin. In the total sample of 425 students, 216 were the foreign student sample and 209 students from each group were the Chinese student sample, with a good recovery rate of 86.4% and 83.6%. Several prior studies analyzing different factors influencing the use of social media support the results of the current report. Social media is most concerned with privacy and convenience, while international and domestic students, on the other hand, largely disregard copyright and legal issues. Years of migration, local language knowledge, level of study, years of migration, and the use of experience affect the level of concern. Among the variables, the level of all applicable factors of concern is clearly influenced by the use of experience. The college students' social media behavior and social media use of transnational communities and Chinese students and their identities are determined by their own individualities and the social-economic factors of their own and host cultures, based on these differences and similarities.

Keywords: Social Media, Transnational Environment, Local Students, International Students, Legal Risk, Credibility, Migration, Privacy, Legal Issues, Copyright

Introduction

More and more students have moved from one country to another for the sake of higher education in recent years. Over the past 40 years, higher education globalization, through student mobility, has evolved considerably (Beine, Noel, & Ragot, 2014). While the key destinations are the United States, the United Kingdom, Germany, France, and Australia, with 6 percent of total international mobility, China has been the leading country in Asia to draw international students. As a consequence of the rapid growth of Chinese education, many of the higher education enrollments of Chinese students have increased. China has made noticeable progress in the education sector in recent decades, especially about increased international student immigration (Nzivo & Chuanfu, 2013). It should be noted here that several scholarships are awarded to foreign students worldwide each year by the Chinese Scholarship Council (CSC). On the other hand, most foreign students enroll as self-financial students at Chinese universities to pursue their higher studies or study the Chinese language. China has become a leading country in Asia for receiving foreign students with 6% of total international mobility, according to CSC results.

In 2012, China recruited 328, 330 foreign students from various countries to study at the best Chinese higher education institutions, a rise of 12% since 2011 (CSC, 2012). The consequence is that the Chinese University Culture has been transformed into a transnational community. However, their link between their home and host countries is fragmented by the positions of transnational cultures and their identities (Levitt & Schiller 2004). The daily rhythms and activities of individuals react not only to more than one state simultaneously within the transnational context, but also to social institutions, such as religious groups, that exist within many states and across their borders (Levitt & Schiller 2004).

The word "transnational" has recently been used instead of international and global (Kauppine 2012) in most social sciences. However, some scholars have argued that among the meanings given to the terms Global, International, and Transnational, there are some inconsistencies (Fong, et al, 2010). Although academicians have inconsistencies, most scholars use the word transnational to describe the communities of immigrant students. Recent scholars consider transnational migration as taking place within a complex social space that is continuously reworked in more than one culture by migrants at the same time. Basch et al (1994) characterize 'transnationalism'

as the process by which immigrants create and maintain multi-stranded social relationships that connect their origins and settlement societies (Basch et al, 1994). Your text will be rewritten. Start by writing something here or pasting it and then press the Paraphrase button.

A strong link exists between transnational society and the technology of communication. Transnational concepts reflect the 'embedding' practices, according to Giddens' Structuralism Theory (1990), which help migrants reconnect amid their physical absence from the community with local structure and institution (Fong. et al, 2010). The use of communication technologies is heavily linked to the development of social relations (McLuhan and Powers, 1989). Understanding technological use and transnational contacts provide an outstanding opportunity to study how this relationship refers to the adaptation of immigrants. Social scientists have long been interested in how to integrate refugees into new nations. Scholars are now increasingly realizing that certain migrants and their descendants continue to be highly affected by their continuing tie to their home country or by nationally enhanced social networking (Levitt & Schiller 2004).

In the host countries, there is a tendency to use newly adopted social media concepts in cultural adaptations during stays in other countries and as an effective and efficient communication tool to communicate with their home countries (Sawyer, 2011). Sawyer claims that the "global village" has brought together people from various cultures through modern social media. In the host countries, there is a tendency to use newly adopted social media concepts in cultural adaptations during stays in other countries and as an effective and efficient communication tool to communicate with their home countries (Sawyer, 2011). People use social media during intercultural adaptation to learn about their host countries, develop and maintain relationships, and keep updated about events with their home nations (Sawyer, 2011).

The world education system has profoundly been reshaped by the rapid growth of social media. Many researchers state that by providing them with knowledge and social support and a way to identify and interact with other students, social media will promote the transfer of students from high school to college. Facebook is the platform most rooted in the lives of U.S. college students among these social media tools (Hargittai, 2007; Smith, Salaway, & Caruso, 2009). Many university students in the world often use social media networks to disseminate and connect with data. From CNNIC. (2009) Statistical Survey Study on China's Internet growth estimated that China, with 162 million Chinese bloggers, dominates the blogosphere worldwide (CNNIC, 2009).

In China, blogging is not just a pastime for opinion leaders, according to Walsh (2008), but a form of collective behavior that emphasizes the cultural need for unity in Chinese society (Walsh 2008). Awareness of technical use and transnational interactions offers an excellent opportunity to research how this relationship relates to the adoption of immigrants. To understand how refugees are integrated into foreign countries, social scientists have long been involved. Scholars have now accepted that some migrants and their descendants remain highly affected by the ongoing relationship with their home country or by national-border social networking (Levitt & Schiller 2004).

Although there are more complicated issues emerging from the use of social media in a transnational context by college students, relatively few research attempts have been made to date. Previous research on migrant students and social media highlights the value of social media as resources for maintaining interpersonal relationships and media access to information and the role of helping migrant students resolve difficulties in a new cultural climate. Factors that impact the adoption of social media by migrant students often fall short. Migrant students form a special group in some countries. The lack of awareness of social media habits would result in the lack of efficiency of education and library services for migrant students, as college teachers, staff and libraries generally use social media to provide services to such students.

Current research aims to explain the real situation on how to use social media to ensure effective social adjustment for college students in the transnational environment. Also, it is time to recognize certain major factors that may be obstacles to the use of social media. Comprehensive research is carried out to understand how migrant students deal with the advantages and risks when they use social media and the disparity between foreign students and local students. This study aims to recognize the key issues when social media is embraced by international students and to concentrate on socio-economic aspects, thus helping educators and librarians design efficient facilities for migrant students. Eight socio-economic factors related to the use of social media were the subject of the study, namely legal risk, privacy, reputation, ease, copyright, expense, time, and permanence.

Our investigation is focused on the following questions:

Q1: What are the major socio-economic concerns when international students using social media?

Q2: What is the difference between international students and local students when facing these concerns? What is the correlation of such concerns with the personal context of international students?

Materials and methods

Test indicators

A meta-analysis of social media is warranted to provide empirical insights regarding various dimensions of international students' use of social media in an intercultural environment. This paper selects text indicators derived from existing researches with a slight adjustment.

Test indicators selection

Test indicators	Sources
Legal risks	Scaife (2015) ; Drucker & Gumpert (2013) ; Cain & Fink (2010)
Privacy	Eddy (2014) ; Dutton, Blank, & Groselj (2013)
Credibility	Sin (2015) ; Tenopir, et al. (2015) ; Schmierbach & Oeldorf-Hirsch (2012)
Convenience	Mandavilli (2011) ; Noorden (2012)
Copyright	Storella (2014)
Cost	Richardson, et al.(2010); Evans.D & McKee J.(2010)
Time	Chittaro & Vianello(2013) ; Lubis, et al.(2012) ; Muench, et al.(2015) ; Tsai & Liu(2015)
Permanency	Hwang & Lee (2014) ; Begum (2015)

(1) Legal risks

A broad description of all business risks with legal consequences is a legal risk here which is characterized as important legal consequences that flow from acts attributable to the organization.

In the virtual world, online legal risks can be present in various activities. Examples of online legal threats of social media include violation of social media terms and conditions, slander, and various forms of infringement, such as infringement of privacy, as well as infringement of trademarks or copyrights. Monitoring of social media pages, social media ads, social media competitions and sweepstakes, and social media publicity coverage insurance should also be taken into account.

(2) Privacy

Privacy of information refers to individuals' ability to access or have some power over information about themselves. It involves: what information must a person disclose to others about oneself or one's associations, under what circumstances and with what safeguards? What items can individuals hold to themselves and not be pressured to report to others? The first instrument developed by Smith, Milberg, and Burke (1996) to measure privacy issues regarding personal information is the scale called "Concern for Information Privacy." This has been named one of the knowledge age's most critical ethical concerns. The advancement of information technology has drawn the attention of researchers to the privacy of information and its impact. Privacy relies on the use of knowledge obtained from social media sites in the sense of social media.

(3) Credibility

Credibility is commonly characterized as the degree to which people find their source's information or credibility, accuracy, and trustworthiness. Given the large number of social media content created by users, the consistency, reliability, and honesty of the information are equally important.

(4) Convenience

For Internet users, the ease of accessing information is important. No matter how good the quality of any source of information might be, it will impact use if it is hard to obtain. There are several sources of information of the same type and the same content in the social media world that offer services in several ways. To some extent, it may reduce the barriers to

accessing information from the user, save time for the user, and increase the quality of accessing information.

(5) Copyright

A type of intellectual property is copyright. In original works of authorship fixed in any tangible medium of speech, now known or subsequently created, copyright protection subsists from which they can be interpreted, copied, or otherwise transmitted, either directly or with the assistance of a computer or device. Copyright includes problems, like who holds the copyright; what are your responsibilities; and what are your rights when your material is converted after cut-and-paste into someone else's profile? Different concerns about copyright violations among college students in China and the US have been published in the literature.

(6) Cost

Cost is one of the variables that must be considered when calculating the importance of sources of information. Typically, irrespective of the rate, it is impossible to obtain information. The costs of buying, researching, borrowing, copying, and other expenditures are included. It involves the cost of network connectivity whether it is an Internet resource; if it involves intellectual property rights, it includes the cost of intellectual property rights and so on.

(7) Time

To access the desired information or service, time is what it takes for a user to search through social media. On the surface, users have not spent too much time in the process of using social media, but the time commitment is important because social media distracts users from their time to participate in other work. Therefore this consumption is equal to the cost of time for the consumer.

(8) Permanency

For research, education, culture, and economic and social growth, documents and data in digital form are relevant, but maintaining their consistency over time is far from a resolved issue. Because of the lack of legal and institutional structures, or because custodians lack expertise, skills, and funding, digital information is lost because its importance is

underestimated. As a digital content carrier, social media also faces the problem of shifting connections, updating content, and so on.

Samples and data collection

The survey method was used to gather information. The sample was chosen from individuals who were studying in China at Wuhan University. The University of Wuhan is an institution where most disciplines are taught with distinctive features. It is one of China's best universities with unique educational achievements. The data collected from the offices of the College of Foreign Students Education and General Administration at Wuhan University shows that in recent years the number of participants from international and local students has gradually increased. Wuhan University was chosen to collect the sample for this research after considering the prominence of the site. From April 26 to May 10, 2019, questionnaires were distributed to 250 foreign students and 250 Chinese students. In the total sample of 425 students, the international student sample consisted of 216 and the Chinese student sample consisted of 209 students from each group, with a successful recovery rate of 86.4% and 83.6%.

When the gender distribution of the international students' sample was considered, it was 54.7% of male students and 45.3% of female students. A complete inspection of the questionnaires of the migrated students shows that 57.52% of the students were from Asian countries while 25.91% from European countries, and 16.57% from African countries. Their language distribution indicates that 16.66% use French as their native language, 13.42% Korean, 13.8% English, 4.62% Russian, 4.62% Hindi, 5.55% Thai, 6.48% Vietnam, 4.62% Urdu, 3.24% Portuguese, 2.31% German, 1.85% Italian, 1.85% Bangla, 4.62% Nepal, 2.31% Sinhala, 2.77% Malagasy, 1.85% Spanish, 4.16% Kazakh, 1.85% Arabic and 0.92% Tamil. These distributions of various language categories prove that Wuhan University consists of a multicultural community from different parts of the world. Greenberg and Ilan(2013) argued that since the students from different native language groups from various cultures and background seek information with some differences in their information behavior and differences in overcoming language barriers, there is a significant difference between native language groups about the use of search engines (Greenberg and Ilan, 2013). The current research also assumes that there may be significant differences among Chinese and international students when they use social media. Therefore, in this study, different factors

that influence the use of social media in multicultural communities studying at Wuhan University were examined.

Variables

It was observed how these independent variables influence the dependent variable. In an experiment, the dependent variable is the event expected to change when the independent variable is manipulated. In this study, the variables under investigation are as follows.

The variables identified in this research are proficiency level, major streams, education level, time duration, experience level/ period.

Three Levels in the Proficiency level are identified; below average, average, and above average.

Three levels in streams were identified; humanities and social sciences, STEM (namely, Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics), and other subjects.

Three levels in education level were identified; undergraduate, master, and doctor

Three levels in time duration were identified; less than 3 years, 3-4 years, and more than 4 years

Three levels in experience level were identified below average, average, and above average.

1. According to listening, speaking, and writing ability in Chinese, the authors divided the respondents' language proficiency level into three groups:

2. According to classification, the authors divide the respondents' majors into

3. According to the academic degree, the authors divide the respondents' educational level into undergraduate, Master, and Doctor.

4. According to the length of time they have spent in studies in China, the authors divide the respondents' study abroad time into less than 3 years, 3-4 years, and more than 4 years.

5. Social media platforms can be divided into the content type and interpersonal type. According to the frequency of access to the two types of platforms, the authors divide the respondents' social media experience into: below average, average, and above average.

Scale development

The questionnaire is designed mainly with structured, close-ended and, open-ended questions, multiple-choice questions, and attitude scale to obtain the necessary information to meet the objective of the study. Structured close-ended types are used as they are normally characterized by a group of fixed responses, and respondents are allowed to choose one or more responses that are designed to reflect various views. A Likert scale is designed to obtain a variety of opinions about respondents attitudes about legal risks, privacy, credibility, convenience, copyright, cost, time, and permanency, to evaluate them by "very important", "important", "general", "not important", and "not important at all" and weigh them 5, 4, 3, 2, 1, respectively. Through calculation, we will discover the influence of different factors on the adoption of social media.

Results

Factors affecting the frequency and amount of social media use:

The current research aims to describe the variables influencing the use of social media. Therefore the factors that influence the usage of social media websites are presented in this data analysis section. It concerns legal risk, privacy, credibility, convenience, copyright, cost, time, and permanency. Statistics show that both international and Chinese students have shown a certain degree of concern about all the factors listed above.

Figure 1: Response to eight factors

Based on their importance, the factors that influence international students in using social media are listed in the following order: privacy, convenience, time spent, cost, legal risk, credibility, permanency, and copyright. For local students, these factors are in the following order: privacy, convenience, credibility, time spent, legal risk, cost, permanency, and copyright. The three factors of cost, stability, and copyright are ranked higher among international students than domestic students.

Figure 2: Average values obtained after assignment to eight factors

Regardless of the influence of variables, privacy, and convenience are always listed as top concerns, and they are the most important influencing factors for international students. Although the factors of cost, permanency, and copyright are ranked higher among international students than local ones, their degree of attention is not the same for the two groups of students. Factors

considered in the use of social media by international students according to the sequence of importance are privacy, convenience, time, cost, legal risk, credibility, permanency, and copyright, while the ranking of these factors by Chinese students are privacy, convenience, credibility, time, legal risk, cost, permanency, and copyright. Thus privacy and convenience have become common important factors affecting international students and Chinese students. On the other hand, they are not highly concerned with permanence and copyright. In contrast, in addition to copyright and cost factors, Chinese students pay more attention to other factors than international students. And, the cognition of the privacy and credibility of social media of the two groups are quite different.

Factors affecting migrated students' cognition of social media

The differences concerning social media may also be linked to socio-economic factors, such as host language proficiency, disciplinary backgrounds, study level, migrated years, or social media experience. Good and bad perceptions of social media vary according to demographic and psychosocial characteristics (Keating, R. T., Hendy, H. M., & Chan, S. H., 2015).

In this part, we list three kinds of calculation results, (1) the number and proportion of respondents (see attachments in Chapter 6); (2) mainly use the mean description; (3) use SPSS to analyze the influence of each factor on 8 concerns, in addition to the experience in social media use; the influence of other factors is not significant.

Host language proficiency

Differences between international students' educational backgrounds and those of the educational systems in which they are enrolled may pose difficulties not encountered by domestic students (Leder & Forgasz, 2004). Many researchers have claimed that the language barrier is one of the main problems facing students in a transnational environment (Mostafa; 2001, Selvadurai; 1992, Cammish; 1997, Macrae;1997)

According to how Thomas and Aithen (1989) have explained, one of the major problems is the language barrier for the students who study overseas. Chinese education system (most universities) has established a mechanism to overcome this language issue by introducing the Chinese language as a mandatory subject for international students. Language improving efforts by international students of a transnational environment lead to facilitate for the adaptation process. In our survey, the mother language of many respondents is not English but they use their

own native languages. Therefore learning the Chinese language will be an advantage for studies and social affairs in the transnational society. Meanwhile, it will be beneficial for approaching social media.

Among migrant students, the Chinese proficiency of 69 respondents (31.9%) is lower than the average level (LP1), 76 people (35.2%) reach the average level (LP2), and 71 (32.9%) (LP3) respondents' levels are higher than the average level. The analysis shows that the cognition of different factors does not show a positive relationship with the improvement of language proficiency. On the factors such as private security, content credibility, convenience, and cost, the attention of the LP1 is higher than LP3. On the contrary, in the aspects of legal risk, copyright protection, and permanency, and so on, LP3 is more concerned about these factors than LP1. This may be because migrant students often solve problems through existing language competence. Students with a low level of Chinese proficiency need to make a higher cognitive effort to get information through social media. Therefore, they pay more attention to those more intuitive factors such as information content and information access methods.

Major difference

According to the statistics of the Council of Graduate Schools, together STEM (science, technology, engineering, and mathematics) fields account for 50% of all applications to U.S. graduate programs from prospective international students for fall 2015. This makes international

graduate students crucial to U.S. research and workforce needs (Council of Graduate Schools, 2015). China has also a huge demand for this high technology immigrant group. STEM education is largely based on the integration of all kinds of resources, social media as an innovative platform to encourage exchanges and cooperation, is more and more applied to STEM Education. Previous research shows significant differences in disciplines. Students in science and engineering tended to use Wikis and Social Q&A more often, and Blogs and Microblogs less often, than did students in humanities and social sciences. Humanities students used Online reviews more often than students in science and engineering (Kim, K., Sin, S., & He, Y, 2013). However, research on migrated students' adoption of social media from the subject point of view is lacking sufficient discussion.

In this research, 117 (56%) of the respondents are from humanities and social sciences, 73 (34.9%) from STEM, and 19 (9.1%) from other areas. We could find that students of humanities and social sciences are concerned more with privacy, credibility, convenience, and copyright issues of concern than the STEM students. While it turns to legal risk, cost, time, permanency, STEM students pay more attention than students of humanities and social sciences. This may be determined by the empirical features of STEM disciplines, and empirical studies need to follow rigorous rules of science and mathematics, rather than imagination. Therefore, they are more likely to understand the issues related to social media from economic rationality.

Study level

In this research, we investigated 103 undergraduate international students (47.9%) (SL1), master's degree 58 (27%) (SL2), doctoral and above 41 (19.1%) (SL3), 13 nonacademic international students (SL4). As can be seen, in addition to legal risks and permanency, SL3 is concerned less about related issues of social media than SL1 and SL2. This may be because professional researchers are not keen on social media; on the contrary, they pay more attention to authoritative information sources.

Through the comparison of cognition of SL1 and SL2, we could find that undergraduate international students focus more on legal risks, copyright, and permanency than migrant students following Master's courses, on the issues of privacy, credibility, convenience, cost, and time, but undergraduates are less concerned.

A previous study showed that undergraduates were more likely to use SNS for ELIS than graduate students, which highlights some of the problems in the application of international students' social media usage. Undergraduate international students may be unable to grasp the use scales of social media, and spend a lot of time and energy on social media, ignoring the protection of their own interests and content evaluation, which leads to some negative consequences.

Migrated years

The sample shows that 151 people (69.9%) have studied in China for 3 years or less (MY1), 45 respondents for 3-4 years (20.8%) (MY 2), 20 people for 4 years or above (9.3%) (MY3).

To a certain extent, the length of migrated time represents the influence of the local environment on students. Studying abroad for 4 years or more basically means he or she has completed the bachelor's or master's degree and has basically adapted to the local learning and lifestyle. After years of the transnational environment of learning, one has formed his value system, and his intercultural characteristics are obvious. 3 years of migrated time means one has just completed the preparation of the language courses, taken up professional learning, gradually familiarized with the local environment, and he is experiencing collision and integration of mental construct. Studying abroad at a younger age makes the cognitive models of migrant students less mature, and their ideas are more likely to be affected by changes in the period of change.

As shown in the following figure, MY1 only pay privacy and convenience a higher level of attention. However, with the growth of the migrated study time, the concern level of credibility and permanency may raise. MY3 pays more attention to credibility, copyright, cost, time, and permanency.

Use of experience

Only 9 (4.2%) respondents' experience of social media use is lower than the average level, 45 people (27.8%) reach the average level, 162 (75%) people's experience in SM use is higher than the average level.

Personal and professional use of social media is related to individual perceptions of social media (Moreno, et al., 2015). With the growth of the social media user experience, international students pay more attention to the relevant issues, and the difference between different groups is very significant. Data shows that serious users of social media consider more comprehensive and in-depth in the adaption of social media. Heavy users concern more than common users, while common users consider more than light users. Direct experience influences more on the formation of attitude and cognition. In the social media environment, experienced international students can obtain a priori knowledge through related services, directly applied to the current information services, to determine the relevant issues.

Discussion

In the use of social media, international students are clearly aware of a variety of risk factors, they measure the risks of using social media comprehensively. However, privacy and convenience

are the factors that they consider first. For the very important factor of copyright, they do not pay enough attention. In comparison, migrated students take copyright issues seriously.

Education affects the cognition of social media usage by international students. Factors that undergraduates pay more attention to than graduates are legal risks (3.88, n=103), copyright (3.75, n=103), time (4.08, n=103) and permanency (3.68, n=103). In contrast, those graduates are concerned more about privacy (4.22, n=58), credibility (3.88, n=58), convenience (4.26, n=58) and cost (3.95, n=58).

Migrated time affects the cognition of social media usage by international students. Those who have spent longer time overseas concern more about social factors including legal risks (3.85, n=20), credibility (3.95, n=20), copyright (3.7, n=20), cost (3.9, n=20), time (4.25, n=20), permanency (3.75, n=20). On the other hand, newly migrant students pay more attention to personal related factors, such as privacy (4.19, n=151) and convenience (4.07, n=151).

Social media use of experience affects the cognition of social media usage by international students. The more the use of social media experience, international students pay more attention to the risk factors. The cognition of factors above-average international students are much higher, namely, privacy (4.3, n=162), time (4.22, n=162), convenience (4.19, n=162), cost (3.97, n=162), credibility (3.97, n=162), legal risks (3.95, n=162), copyright (3.77, n=162) and permanency (3.77, n=162). What under average migrant students concern most is permanency (2.89, n=9) and cost (2.56, n=9); they do not care about convenience (2.33, n=9).

Conclusion

The findings of the current research confirm several previous studies investigating multiple factors affecting the use of social media. Social media is most concerned with privacy and convenience, while copyright and legal concerns are mostly overlooked by foreign and domestic students, the contrary. The level of concern is influenced by the years of migration, local language competence, level of study, years of migration, and the use of experience. Among the variables, the use of experience clearly affects the degree of all relevant factors of concern.

Research findings imply that there is a significant difference between native language groups about the use of social media. Further, this study finds that the different factors influence the use

of social media of multicultural communities from different parts of the world studying at Wuhan University. When considering a major study area and 8 factors, a variation of using social media can be observed even among the student in the same major subjects. It can be noticed that the perception of individuals causes this factor. The usage of social media would be determined by the expectation of the students in the transnational environment and the factors that influence the use of social media is also determined by the so-called individual expectation of students. Moreover, current research reveals that factors, affecting over differences and similarities of social Media used by International and Chinese students.

In discussing similarities between Chinese and international students in the use of social media, both Chinese and international students are greatly concerned about the legal risk. However, in both groups, the least number of students think that the legal risks and issues that may have negative effects on one's using social media. Although social media like facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, blogs, wikis, and other virtual communities help create new opportunities to build up diverse relationships with each other, there are many inherent legal risks that everyone has to face unenthusiastically. Moreover, a substantial number of studies on social media and legal risks have claimed that online opportunities and risks are interconnected (Sonia, 2009). Also, this study further verifies this factor in previous studies. This research can conclude that when university students are more concerned about legal risk, the frequency with which they use social media sites decreases. This can be identified as a barrier to the use of social media by Chinese and international students. Both study groups claim that convenience is one of the most important factors that affect the use of social media. Many researchers have claimed that both usefulness and enjoyment factors affect motivation in the use of information technology systems (Davis, F. D. 1989). Ellahi and Bokhari (2012) claimed that user-friendliness is mainly affected by the use of social media. Related to these factors, the current research discovers that the convenience of use of social media directly affects the highest usage of social media. While the usage of social media is more convenient, it helps increase the usability of social media, and the inconvenience of the use of social media stands as a barrier to the use of social media.

Although previous studies emphasize that social media have become more integrated into the host culture during their adaptation, the international students' expectation of the highest amount of credibility of using social media may badly influence in establishing and maintaining

relationships with their host culture. On the other hand, when Chinese students do not care about the credibility of social media it increases the use of social media by local university students. This is a clear difference between Chinese and international students.

The current study reveals that compared to international students, Chinese students are more concerned about the privacy of social media. In the context of social media, privacy is important because it helps increase trust in users, which can lead to increased use of social media sites. Some researchers have identified six different significant factors that affect users' perceptions of quality in the context of social networking websites. Among six factors, they have named privacy as an important factor (Ellahi and Bokhari, 2013) Anyway most researches suggest that social media helps everyone to learn things about people in the world. Claypoole (2014) discusses that social media may help create communities, but it also destroys privacy. Therefore he further mentions that in Europe, Canada, and other countries across the world, protection of each citizen's private information is considered to be a human right, secured by states and enforced by the government and private causes of action. Further analysis shows that in the United States, by contrast, only certain classes of information are protected under Federal law (Claypoole (2014)). The University of Michigan has published an article on Guidelines for the use of social media. According to these guidelines, it says that the rapid growth of social media combined with their ease of use and pervasiveness make them attractive channels of communication. However social media hold the possibility of a host of unintended consequences. Further, to avoid these consequences, the guidance suggests social media users' safety and privacy tips for social media networking (Guidelines for the use of Social Media, 2010). On the other hand, compared to Chinese students, international students are more concerned about copyright when they use social media. This means international students are more concerned about the rights of the authors and creators of works in social media.

Research reveals that both groups of students have importantly concerned about the time when they use social media. However, when compared to international students, Chinese students are more concerned about time. This means international students are more likely to engage with social media. Now scholars increasingly recognize that some migrants and their descendants remain strongly influenced by their continuing tie to their home country or by social networking that strengthens across national borders (Levitt & Schiller, 2004). Social media have become more

integrated into the host culture during their adaptation and to maintain connections to their home countries (Sawyer, 2011). Sawyer argues that new social media has brought people from different cultures together in the "global village". During the intercultural adaptation, people use social media to learn about their host countries, establish and maintain relationships, and stay informed about events with their home countries. On the findings of this study, we can conclude that most students are addicted to the use of social media to escape from negative feelings, learn their host culture, and continuing bond with their home country. Concerning other factors such as cost, both student groups are concerned about it as considerable factors that affect the use of social media. The three factors of "cost, stability, copyright" are ranked higher among migrated students than domestic students.

It can be concluded that Current research reveals factors, affecting over differences and similarities of social Media, used by International and Chinese students. According to these differences and similarities, adaptation behavior and social media usage of transnational communities and Chinese students and their identities are decided by their own individualities and the social-economic factors of their own and host cultures. Finally, for international students, the use of social media to discover useful digital resources is an effective way to adjust themselves to the new learning and living environment. The major contributing factors for their use of social media are privacy, convenience, and time spent. Based on this finding, social media providers should make improvements to protect user privacy. As migrated students depend heavily on social media for their learning, research needs as well as their daily life in today's digital environment, it is important for university administrators to integrate media literacy education into academic training and professional development programs for both migrated students and faculty. When media literacy education is provided, we also need to tailor it to people needs by paying attention to their differences in gender, age, discipline enrolled, country of origin, host language proficiency, and to help migrated students take advantage of the social media and to better protect their interests.

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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